

ASSESSMENT OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION ON THE PROCESSES OF MYOCARDIAL REMODELING IN CORONARY HEART DISEASE, AGGRAVATED BY TYPE 2 DIABETES

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Abstract

The purpose of the study. To study the effect of endothelin-1 and endothelial growth factor on the development of endothelial dysfunction and processes of myocardial remodeling in patients with coronary artery disease.

Materials and methods: During the study, all patients and representatives of CG included in the study were examined, during which the structural and functional state of the myocardium (echocardiography - EchoCG) and the features of the functional state of the endothelium (endothelium-dependent vasodilation test, concentration of VEGF and ET-1) were studied.

Results: Ischemic myocardial remodeling is characterized by dilation of the heart cavities, spherical deformation of the LV cavity, thinning of the walls, an increase in LVEF, and an increase in the time to achieve an effective pressure gradient between chambers (Tei). Structural and functional remodeling of the myocardium is accompanied by a decrease in regional and global contractility of the left and right ventricles, as well as a violation of active diastolic relaxation, and the formation of postcapillary pulmonary hypertension.

Factors associated with LV systolic dysfunction in patients with coronary heart disease are LV remodeling and dilation (HR=3.02, $p<0.001$), three-vessel coronary lesion (HR=3.48, $p<0.001$), VEGF concentration in venous blood above 654 pg/ml (HR=3.44, $p<0.001$), concentration of ET-1 in venous blood is higher than 1.95fmol/L (HR=2.33, $p<0.01$).

Conclusions: In patients with coronary artery disease with myocardial remodeling, the concentration of VEGF and ET-1 is more than 10 times higher than the values typical for healthy individuals. The concentration of VEGF and ET-1 in venous blood correlates with the severity of pathological myocardial remodeling and the degree of EDV impairment.

Keywords: coronary heart disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus, endothelium dysfunctions.

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are the leading cause of death worldwide (Global atlas on cardiovascular disease prevention and control. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2011). It is estimated that 17.3 million people died from CVD in 2008, accounting for 30% of all deaths worldwide. Currently, coronary heart disease remains one of the most pressing problems of the internal medicine clinic, due to both the prevalence of cardiovascular diseases in the population and their contribution to the mortality structure [1,2,3]. The interest in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases is determined by the widespread occurrence of coronary heart disease (CHD), its leading role in the causes of disability and mortality of the population, which gives the problem not only medical but also social significance [4,5]. By the beginning of the 21st century, the attention of clinicians focused on the role of endothelial dysfunction in the formation of coronary heart disease [6,7,8]. Endothelial dysfunction (DE) is an imbalance between the production of vasodilating, antiproliferative factors (NO, prostacyclin, tissue plasminogen activator, C-type natriuretic peptide, endothelial hyperpolarizing factor) on the one hand and vasoconstrictive, prothrombotic, proliferative factors (endothelin, superoxide anion, thromboxane A₂, tissue activator inhibitor plasminogen) - with the other one. The leading role in the development of the latter belongs to a violation of

the bioavailability of endothelium-produced nitric oxide (NO), activation of endothelin 1 and a decrease in vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) [1].

Disruption of the structure and function of the endothelium in coronary heart disease has a significant effect on the tone and thrombogenicity of the vascular wall, and the neurohormones produced by it can exacerbate vascular and cardiac remodeling [1,9]. Markers of endothelial dysfunction and damage are a decrease in endothelium-dependent vascular vasodilation (EDVD), changes in the blood content of regulatory peptides: endothelin-1, prostacyclin, Willebrand factor, growth factor, and an increased number of circulating desquamated endothelial cells [6, 10].

Considering the above, it is of interest to study the clinical, hemodynamic and humoral markers of the development of endothelial dysfunction during the course of the disease and remodeling processes in patients with coronary artery disease.

The purpose of the study. To study the effect of endothelin-1 and endothelial growth factor on the development of endothelial dysfunction and processes of myocardial remodeling in patients with coronary artery disease.

Research material The study included 108 patients with coronary heart disease who are under outpatient supervision in the RCNPT and MR. The diagnosis was

based on the clinical picture – clinical signs of angina pectoris of functional classes II-III, a history of myocardial infarction (MI) or electrocardiographic signs. The verification of the diagnosis was based on coronary angiography and coronary revascularization. Background diseases such as hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, insulin resistance syndrome (according to the insulin resistance index in patients with glycemic levels within the reference standards), and hyperuricemia were recorded in all patients. Criteria for inclusion in the study: 1) verified (coronarographically) coronary artery disease, stable course; 2) regular (at least 3 months before inclusion in the study) intake of basic therapy for coronary artery disease, including beta blockers, antiplatelet agents, statins, neprilysin receptor antagonists; 3) age of patients 25-70 years; 4) consent of patients to be included in the study. Criteria for non-inclusion of patients in the study: 1) febrile condition of any etiology; 2) malignant neoplasms or benign neoplasms requiring treatment; 3) destabilization of the course of coronary heart disease during the previous 2 months; 4) persistent form of atrial fibrillation; 5) terminal period of organ failure. The average age of the patients was 55.94 ± 1.29 years, height – 170.24 ± 1.12 cm, weight – 77.72 ± 1.79 kg. As a control group (KG), the study included 20 healthy volunteers without signs of damage to the cardiovascular system, of comparable age and anthropometric characteristics. 74 patients had a history of MI, including 18 patients with 2 and 10 patients with 3 MI. All patients included in the study underwent diagnostic coronary angiography during the previous year. According to the results of the study, all patients were distributed depending on the number of affected pools. 53 patients (49.07%) underwent CA stenting, 21 patients (19.44%) underwent surgical revascularization.

Research methods: During the study, all patients and representatives of CG included in the study were examined, during which the structural and functional state of the myocardium (echocardiography - EchoCG) and the features of the functional state of the endothelium (endothelium-dependent vasodilation test, concentration of VEGF and ET-1) were studied.

The follow-up period was 3 months, after which a follow-up examination of the condition of the myocardium and endothelium was performed.

The VEGF concentration was determined in serum obtained from peripheral venous blood. Blood sampling was performed in the morning on an empty stomach in a supine position after 10 minutes of rest, from the cubital vein, with a vacuum cleaner. Excessive physical activity was excluded the day before. The blood was centrifuged to produce serum. The VEGF concentration was measured by solid-phase enzyme immunoassay using a set of VEGF-ELISA-BEST reagents manufactured by Vector-Best CJSC (Russia) with a measuring range of 6.25-4000 pg/ml, the reference norm in blood serum was 6.25-600 pg/ml.

The concentration of ET-1 was determined in peripheral venous blood obtained by a vacutainer from the ulnar vein. Blood sampling was performed in the morning on an empty stomach, in a supine position, after excluding fatty foods and excessive physical exertion on the eve. The measurement was carried out by enzyme

immunoassay, using a Humareader HS, "HUMAN" Germany analyzer, the range of values was 0-10 mmol/L.

The EchoCG examination was performed on a Philips "Affiniti 50G" ultrasound scanner (the Netherlands) using a sector sensor with color mode and pulse-wave, continuous-wave mode with a frequency of 2-4 MHz in standard echocardiographic positions in M- and B-modes according to the recommendations of the American Echocardiographic Society (ASE) (Schiller N.B. et al., 1989). The examination was performed in the morning in the patient's position on the left side and on the back, after a 10-minute rest. The examination included scanning using standard ultrasound windows and EchoCG positions. The study protocol included recording the parameters of the structural and functional state of the heart and the characteristics of intracardiac blood flow.

The assessment of endothelium-dependent vasodilation was based on a change in the diameter of the brachial artery at the 5th second after arterial decompression during a 5-minute cuff test. The diameter of the artery was determined sonographically 2 cm above the elbow. The Philips "Affiniti 50G" ultrasound scanner (the Netherlands), equipped with a linear sensor with a frequency of 15 mhz, was used. The dynamics of the brachial artery diameter and flow velocity were recorded as a relative change, expressed as a percentage.

The technique is based on an increase in the expression of nitric oxide by endotheliocytes in response to an increase in the shear stress of the surface membrane with an increase in blood flow velocity (against the background of compression, ischemia of the peripheral extremities occurs, the accumulation of under-oxidized products causes peripheral vasodilation and deficiency of the microcirculatory bed. When compression is removed, filling of the expanded peripheral vascular bed leads to an increase in blood flow velocity in the PA segment under study and an increase in shear stress on the endothelium).

Statistical processing. All the results of the study were entered into the summary tables of the Microsoft Office Excel editor. During statistical processing, all the individuals included in the study were divided into groups according to the study design. All the parameters studied followed a normal distribution. In the case of parametric quantities, the arithmetic mean and its standard error were determined as characteristics of the group. The intergroup comparison was carried out using the Student's confidence criterion for paired and unpaired values. Multiple comparisons were also performed using the Student's criterion. The correlation analysis was performed using the Pearson criterion and evaluating its reliability based on the tables, taking into account the number of correlated pairs.

Research results. The study found that humoral markers of endothelial dysfunction were significantly increased in patients with coronary heart disease compared with the group of healthy volunteers (Table 2). Thus, the concentration of VEGF and IL-6 in patients with coronary heart disease was increased 4-fold ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.007$, respectively), ET-1 - in 10 times ($p < 0.603$).

Correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between VEGF concentration and the number of affected coronary basins ($r=0.84$, $p<0.01$), as well as an average positive relationship between ET-1

concentration and the number of affected basins ($r=0.68$, $p<0.01$) and between ET-1 concentration and VEGF concentration ($r=0.68$, $p<0.01$).

Table 2

Comparative characteristics of the structural and functional state of the endothelium in patients with coronary heart disease and healthy individuals

Index	Main group ¹	Comparison group ²	Control group ³	p
D -dimer, ng/ml	292,415±35,862	287,606±47,767	124,85±21,24	¹⁻² 0,01 ²⁻³ 0,302 ¹⁻³ 0,05
IL-6, pg/ml	41,4±4,16	27,58±2,92	13,35±1,33	¹⁻² 0,007 ²⁻³ 0,001 ¹⁻³ 0,001
Endothelin - 1, pg/ml	175,58±39,97	147,18±37,13	16,95±1,75	¹⁻² 0,603 ²⁻³ 0,001 ¹⁻³ 0,001
VEGF, pg/ml	938,58±55,23	702,92±48,34	241,89±28,6	¹⁻² 0,001 ²⁻³ 0,03 ¹⁻³ 0,02

Note: * - the reliability of the difference between the groups. One character – $p<0.05$, two characters - $p<0.01$, three characters - $p<0.001$.

Functional vascular remodeling was also characterized by a 2.34-fold decrease in the degree of endothelium-dependent vasodilation compared with healthy individuals ($p<0.001$). In the group of patients with coronary heart disease, the majority of patients (55.55%) had insufficient ESRD (less than 10%), and 11.11% of patients had paradoxical vasoconstriction.

In patients with coronary artery disease, despite the development of endothelial dysfunction, the diameter of the PA did not differ from the diameter of the vessel in the group of healthy individuals, both initially and after 5-minute compression of the artery.

Correlation analysis showed that there is a significant negative relationship between the value of EDV and the concentration of markers of endothelial dysfunction: strong with a concentration of VEGF ($r=-0.80$, $p<0.01$) and moderate with a concentration of ET-1 ($r=-0.61$, $p<0.01$).

Analysis of the dynamics of maximum blood flow velocities in the PA revealed that at all stages of the study in patients with coronary artery disease, the maximum velocity was lower than in the group of healthy volunteers (1.21 times initially, 1.51 times on the 5th and 1.39 times on the 60th second of decompression), with a lower degree of speed increase after removal compressions: thus, the relative dynamics by the 5th second of decompression in the IHD group was $20.48\pm 0.59\%$ versus $51.25\pm 3.48\%$ in KG (dynamics 2.50 times less, $p<0.001$), by 60-1 seconds – $10.19\pm 0.36\%$ and $26.20\pm 1.50\%$, respectively (2.57 times less, $p<0.001$).

Correlation analysis showed the presence of significant negative associations between the blood flow rate in the PA at all stages of the test with humoral markers of endothelial dysfunction, more pronounced with the concentration of VEGF and less pronounced with the concentration of ET-1.

An EchoCG study revealed that in patients with coronary heart disease, dilation of all chambers of the heart was noted in comparison with KG (Table.3): the

increase in LP in patients with coronary heart disease compared with CG was 59.27%, LV – by 37.86%, RV – by 31.56% and PP – by 49.18% (the reliability of intergroup differences for all indicators is $p<0.001$). The thickness of the MBP in patients with coronary heart disease was significantly higher (by 10.72%) compared with KG ($p<0.01$), reflecting myocardial hypertrophy in response to ischemic apoptosis. The thickness of the CSF in the groups did not differ. The predominance of dilation over hypertrophy led to a significant decrease in the OTC index in patients with coronary heart disease (by 14.74%, the significance of intergroup differences was $p<0.01$). Dilation of the heart cavities was accompanied by measurement of the geometry of the cavities, as LVH in patients with coronary heart disease increased by 18.88% ($p<0.001$).

LV myocardial mass in patients with coronary artery disease was increased by 90.06% compared to KG ($p<0.001$). Thus, in the group of patients with coronary heart disease, the majority of patients (93 people – 86.11%) had LV hypertrophy (LVH, LVEF 110 g/m² or more).

LV systolic function was characterized in patients with coronary heart disease by an increase in INRS, reflecting regional contractility disorders, compared with CG (by 53.09%, $p<0.001$), as well as a decrease in total systolic function, LVEF (-14.00% relative to CG, $p<0.001$).

The systolic function of the pancreas was characterized by a decrease in the FUP index, an analogue of the RV for the pancreas, calculated by area due to the complex geometry of the pancreatic cavity. The LVF in patients with coronary heart disease was 8.27% less than in KG ($p<0.05$).

Diastolic function revealed various variants of dysfunction in 100% of patients with coronary heart disease, while in KG diastolic dysfunction was observed only in 11 patients (10.97%, the significance of an intergroup difference in the frequency of various types of diastolic dysfunction between groups chi

squared $4 \times 2 = 57.67$, $p < 0.001$). Among the disorders of diastolic function, the variant of delayed relaxation prevailed.

The diastolic filling of the pancreas was also impaired in patients with coronary heart disease (59.26% of patients), while in representatives of KG the diastolic filling was normal (the reliability of the intergroup difference in the frequency of occurrence of various diastolic filling variants chi squared $2 \times 4 = 23.70$, $p < 0.001$).

Impaired LV diastolic and systolic function in patients with coronary heart disease led to an increase in the average pressure in the LP cavity and in the LA system by 64.17% ($p < 0.001$). In 80 patients of the CHD

group (74.07%), the average pressure in the LA, determined by the ratio of acceleration time to expulsion time on the LA valve, exceeded the normal value (19 mmHg).

The study examined the Tei index, an integral index of myocardial functioning that characterizes the efficiency of the myocardium, that is, the time required for effective changes in intraventricular pressure. In patients with coronary heart disease, the Tei index was increased compared with the CG index (by 27.19% for LV, $p < 0.01$, and 18.35% for RV, nd).

Table 3

Comparative characteristics of the structural and functional state of the myocardium in patients with coronary heart disease and healthy individuals

Index	Control group	Main group
index of the left atrium, ml/m ²	26,90±1,75	42,84±0,87***
index of the left ventricle, ml/m ²	51,55±1,55	71,06±2,20***
LVEF, % (Simpson)	61,00±1,25	52,46±0,94***
left ventricular myocardial mass index, g/m ²	87,20±2,52	165,73±4,93***
total wall thickness, relative	0,37±0,01	0,31±0,01**
ventricular septum, mm	9,40±0,23	10,41±0,19**
posterior wall of the left ventricle, mm	9,55±0,20	9,61±0,12
sphericity index, relative	0,54±0,07	0,64±0,01***
index of violation of regional contractility, score	1,00±0,00	1,53±0,04***
LV Tei, rel .	0,60±0,01	0,77±0,06**
mean pulmonary artery pressure, mmHg	14,85±0,27	24,38±0,68***
RV Tei, relative	0,63±0,01	0,75±0,06
index of the right ventricle, cm ² /m ²	19,70±0,54	25,91±0,70***

Note: * - the reliability of the difference between the groups. One character - $p < 0.05$, two characters - $p < 0.01$, three characters - $p < 0.001$.

Correlation analysis showed the presence of a significant relationship between the concentration of humoral factors of endothelial function VEGF and ET-1 and the characteristics of myocardial remodeling: a positive relationship with the volume of the chambers of the heart, LVEF, INRS, cpR LA and RVF, and a negative relationship with the thickness of the LVL, the value of OTC, LVEF. The association is more significant with the concentration of VEGF compared with the concentration of ET-1.

Thus, coronary heart disease is associated with a marked decrease in the degree of endothelium-dependent vasodilation in 56% of patients, and in 11% of patients with paradoxical vasoconstriction.

Ischemic myocardial remodeling is characterized by dilation of the heart cavities, spherical deformation of the LV cavity, thinning of the walls, an increase in LVEF, and an increase in the time to achieve an effective pressure gradient between chambers (Tei). Structural and functional remodeling of the myocardium is accompanied by a decrease in regional and global contractility of the left and right ventricles, as well as a violation of active diastolic relaxation, and the formation of postcapillary pulmonary hypertension.

Factors associated with LV systolic dysfunction in patients with coronary heart disease are LV remodeling and dilation (HR=3.02, $p < 0.001$), three-vessel coronary lesion (HR=3.48, $p < 0.001$), VEGF concentration in ve-

nous blood above 654 pg/ml (HR=3.44, $p < 0.001$), concentration of ET-1 in venous blood is higher than 1.95fmol/L (HR=2.33, $p < 0.01$).

In patients with coronary artery disease with myocardial remodeling, the concentration of VEGF and ET-1 is more than 10 times higher than the values typical for healthy individuals. The concentration of VEGF and ET-1 in venous blood correlates with the severity of pathological myocardial remodeling and the degree of EDV impairment.

References

1. Ельский В.Н., Вагунин Н.Т., Калинкина Н.В., Салахова А.М. (2008) Роль дисфункции эндотелия в генезе сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний. Журн. АМН України, 14(1): 51–62.
2. Abhinand C.S., Raju R., Soumya S.J., Arya P.S., Sudhakaran P.R. VEGF-A/VEGFR2 signaling network in endothelial cells relevant to angiogenesis. J. Cell Commun. Signal. 2016;10:347–354. doi: 10.1007/s12079-016-0352-8.
3. Anand I., McMurray J., Cohn J.N., Konstam M.A., Notter T., Quitzau K., Ruschitzka F., Lüscher T.F. Long-term effects of darusentan on left-ventricular remodeling and clinical outcomes in the Endothelin A Receptor Antagonist Trial in Heart Failure (EARTH): Randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. Lancet. 2004;364:347–354. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(04)16723-8.
4. Bohm F., Jensen J., Svane B., Settergren M., Pernow J. Intracoronary endothelin receptor blockade

- improves endothelial function in patients with coronary artery disease. *Can. J. Physiol. Pharmacol.* 2008;86:745–751. doi: 10.1139/Y08-081. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
5. Chen J., Chen M.-H., Guo Y.-L., Zhu C.-G., Xu R.-X., Dong Q., Li J.-J. Plasma Big Endothelin-1 Level and the Severity of New-onset Stable Coronary Artery Disease. *J. Atheroscler. Thromb.* 2015;22:126–135. doi: 10.5551/jat.26401.
 6. Park J.E., Keller G.A., Ferrara N. The vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) isoforms: Differential deposition into the subepithelial extracellular matrix and bioactivity of extracellular matrix-bound VEGF. *Mol. Biol. Cell.* 1993;4:1317–1326. doi: 10.1091/mbc.4.12.1317.
 7. Peach C.J., Mignone V.W., Arruda M.A., Alcobia D.C., Hill S.J., Kilpatrick L.E., Woolard J. Molecular Pharmacology of VEGF-A Isoforms: Binding and Signalling at VEGFR2. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2018;19:1264. doi: 10.3390/ijms19041264
 8. Shen J., Xie Y., Liu Z., Zhang S., Wang Y., Jia L., Wang Y., Cai Z., Ma H., Xiang M. Increased myocardial stiffness activates cardiac microvascular endothelial cell via VEGF paracrine signaling in cardiac hypertrophy. *J. Mol. Cell. Cardiol.* 2018;122:140–151. doi: 10.1016/j.yjmcc.2018.08.014.
 9. Shin A.N., Dasgupta C., Zhang G., Seal K., Zhang L. Proteomic Analysis of Endothelin-1 Targets in the Regulation of Cardiomyocyte Proliferation. *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.* 2017;17:1788–1802. doi: 10.2174/1568026617666161116142417.
 10. Wang Y., Tang Y., Zou Y., Wang D., Zhu L., Tian T., Wang J., Bao J., Hui R., Kang L., et al. Plasma level of big endothelin-1 predicts the prognosis in patients with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy. *Int. J. Cardiol.* 2017;243:283–289.